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The Ethical Example of Old Testament Prophets as a Framework for Addressing Moral Decline in Pastoral Ministry in Nigeria

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Abstract

The ethical example of Old Testament prophets like Elijah, Amos, Jeremiah and Isaiah refers to their moral, courage, accountability, and uncompromising proclamation of divine truth. Moral decline in pastoral ministry denotes greed, sexual misconduct, financial impropriety, materialism, and silence on societal evils among Nigeria clergy. The aim of this paper is to establish a prophetic ethical framework to correct pastoral moral failures in Nigeria. The study used qualitative, biblical-theological approach using Old Testament texts and prophets Jeremiah, Elijah, Amos as examples, Nigerian church reports and scholarly works on pastoral ethics. A virtue ethics theoretical framework, grounded in a prophetic role in morality, truth-telling, integrity, and courage as corrective norms, was adopted. The study finds that the ethical example of Old Testament prophets offers four corrective pillars: fearless confrontation of power, public advocacy against injustice, offering godly counsel on national and moral issues and live in absolute obedience to God. In addition, Nigerian pastoral moral decline often stems from compromised accountability, which these models directly address. This paper concluded that adopting the Old Testament prophetic example provides a viable framework for restoring moral authority in Nigerian pastoral ministry.

Keywords: Pastoral Ministry, Nigeria, Pastors, Prophets, Moral Decline, Old Testament Prophets

Introduction

According to Kramer (1972), a prophet is "a person who speaks for God; one who foretells, an inspired preacher." The Hebrew term *nāḇī* (spokesperson) traditionally translates as "prophet." The second division of the Tanakh (Nevi'im) is devoted to Hebrew prophets. Deuteronomy 18:18 describes the prophet as one in whom God places His words to speak to the people. Prophets served as intermediaries between God and humans (Bullock, 1986). Their messages included judgment, encouragement, mercy, and hope for the future. They addressed local, national, and international issues, warning of consequences while offering exhortations that promote spiritual devotion and divine blessing rather than destruction (Wright, 2010). They are best recognized as charismatic individuals compelled by divine experience to speak Yahweh's words despite opposition, mockery, imprisonment, and persecution. Thus, this godly, ethical, and moral example of the Old Testament prophets, especially Elijah, Jeremiah, Isaiah, and Amos, necessitated this research to serve as a framework for addressing moral decline in pastoral ministry in Nigeria.

This study, therefore, explores Old Testament prophetic ethics as a solution to Nigeria's pastoral moral decline. Primary data come from biblical passages on morality, prophets, and integrity; secondary data from books, journals, and online sources. The study adopts virtue ethics, which focuses on the character of the moral agent, i.e. the pastor. It seeks to understand what kind of person a pastor should become. The Old Testament prophets exemplify specific virtues such as boldness, truth-telling, humility, obedience to God, integrity, and others. Moreover, virtue ethics provides the theoretical justification for imitating these prophetic traits. Instead of merely creating anti-corruption policies, the Nigerian pastoral ministry needs character formation that internalises prophetic virtues. Moral decline, from this viewpoint, is a failure of character, not just a breach of codes.

The aim of this research is to examine how the ethical lifestyle of Old Testament prophets can serve as a remedy for the moral decline observed in contemporary pastoral ministry in Nigeria, and the specific objectives are to:

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- i. highlight the transformational roles of Old Testament prophets as mediators, interpreters of the law, social justice advocates and spiritual leaders.
 - ii. examine the causes of moral failures in Nigerian pastoral ministry, including love of money, materialism, insufficient knowledge of the Bible, lack of integrity and others.
 - iii. propose a reorientation of pastoral ministry based on prophetic ethics such as integrity, humility, courage and selflessness in order to restore moral credibility and national transformation.

Ethical Lifestyle of Prophets in the Old Testament

The will to actions in prophetic movement is prompted by a dual purpose:

(1) to hold the people steadfast to Yahweh, their sole Guardian and Law Giver; and (2) to create a spiritually self-sufficient, unified people whose life and institutions should be based on justice and austere simplicity. In a sense the two are but one principle, inspired by the tradition of Moses.

With this tradition as an accepted guide, the prophets believed that Israel would be a peculiar people and that it would reject all incompatible phases of Palestinian or Semitic civilization (Hill 1986). The prophet's primary mission is to communicate the truth about Yahweh, to warn and admonish in order that judgment may be averted (Jer. 35:15). The prophecy was not for the future but for the present. The ethical examples of prophets Jeremiah, Elijah, and Amos in the Old Testament shall be discussed under the following headings:

1. ***The Prophet as Intermediary:*** Despite the multiple roles assumed by the prophets of the Old Testament, it is still possible to identify one element common to all the prophets. The Israelite prophets functioned as intermediaries between the human and the divine worlds, and represented humans to God (e.g., Amos 7:2) and God to humans (Amos 5:4). They acted with the power of God within the mundane world. They envisioned the cosmic world (Amos 7:4; Zech 1:7-17) and sometimes participated in the divine council (1 Kg 22; Isa. 6). The prophets often analyzed the machinations of humans (Micah 3) (Herbert, 1940). They are truly boundary figures. The prophets spoke for God to the people, calling the people to respond faithfully to the God who had revealed Himself in their history. They also spoke for the weak, the oppressed, the disenfranchised, those who had little voice in shaping their own

lives or their own future. Moreover, as they were speaking for the people, they were equally speaking for God, because their tradition remembered that once they were slaves in Egypt with no voice in their own future until God entered history and delivered them. Such oppression of the helpless by the powerful was understood by the prophets to be a violation of the most fundamental part of God's revelation of Himself, that He is the kind of God who hears the cries of oppressed slaves and responds with grace and deliverance (Koch, 1983).

2. ***The Prophet as Watchman:*** In looking at Old Testament prophets more closely, Lewis claimed that it is clear that their message is most often calling the people back to proper worship of God (1989). But much of that task is done in the context of the community, the nation of Israel. That meant that much of the criticism of the prophets is leveled at religious leaders for their failure to be spiritual leaders. It is also aimed at the powerful, most often the religious leaders, who use their power and influence for selfish or sinful purposes, and sometimes not only forsake Yahweh but also teach their subjects to do the same (Lewis, 1989). In the time of the monarchs, Yahwism (that is, the worship of Yahweh), the religion of Israel went through a series of challenges. This is evident in the constant struggle between Yahwism and the Canaanite nature religions. It went to the extent that the nature of primitive Yahwism had long been forgotten in Israel. The consequence of this is that in many minds, the essential distinction between Yahweh and the pagan gods had been blurred (Okwueze, 1998). Thus, Yahwism was in danger of slipping unawares into outright polytheism. This situation calls for reforms, and the prophets made the early attempts at reforming Yahwism. As loyal Yahwists, the prophets fought rigorously for the enthronement of Yahweh in the national life of Israel. Elijah's activities can be understood against the backdrop of this prevailing situation. As deep religious thinkers, the prophets saw the shift of allegiance from Yahweh to the emerging world powers in the ancient Near East as an abomination. The prophet sees Yahweh as the Lord over all creation, and all powers were subject to him. To enter into any alliance, therefore, portends undermining the person of Yahweh (Isaiah 30:1-7) (Fohrer, 1972)

3. *The Prophet as Crusader:* Israel and Judah had undergone drastic sociocultural, economic and political development. The prophets would appear on the national scene to remind the people of the essence of their being as a people and as a nation. They served as a balance to the unrestrained power of the monarchy and the aristocracy (1 Sam 8:11-17). Politically, the crown no longer took cognisance of the poor and the ancestral law (1 Kg. 21); hence, a prophet like Elijah would not spare the crown in his utter condemnation of the king's tyranny (Coogan, 2008). So, the prophets stand as a countervoice to those who would allow the allure of power, ambition, and self-serving self-righteousness to blind them to the things of God: doing justice, loving mercy, and walking humbly with God. The state, with its taxation and its civil service, had brought about a further disintegration of the old social order in Israel.

In this way, as clearly stated by Obbink (1939), urbanisation, with its attendant sociocultural and economic evils, becomes a necessary evil. The great landowners living in the towns gained control over the village people, resulting in severe social injustice. Because of the burden of taxation, the peasant who were economically weak were no longer able to maintain their land. The village people became increasingly poor (Isaiah 5:8, Micah 2:1f). Consequently, the prophets condemned in clear terms those who exploited and despised the poor (cf. Is. 3:14-15; Amos 2:6; 4:1; 8:4-8). They spoke out particularly to challenge, in God's name, those who made laws that allowed the poor to be exploited (Is. 10:1-2, Jer. 22:3). This condemnation of unjust legislators was matched equally by strong words against unjust judges (Amos 5:12) (Coogan, 2008).

The prophets called them rather to live out Torah as a faithful response to God. They called the people to abandon the status quo shaped by those who benefited from it most, to embrace a new future shaped, empowered, and energized by God (Vonrad, 1995). They are empowered by a vision of how things could be, a future in which the people and their leaders would live out their calling to be the people of God as a channel of blessing to the world. They had the courage to call into question any preoccupation with the status quo on any level that interfered with that future. As a result, they were often in trouble with

- those who stand to lose most if the status quo were to be changed and that "could be" future became a reality.
4. ***The Prophet as Spiritual Director:*** Pedersen (1946) succinctly asserted that a rereading of the historical and prophetic books in the light of the course also depicts the role of a prophet as a military strategist. Most often, when an Israelite king was strategizing for war, especially in case of doubts, the prophets would be consulted to inquire the mind of Yahweh (cf. 1 Sam. 28:6, 14ff; I Kg 20). Prophet Isaiah was actively involved in the prosecution of the Syro-Ephraimite war and the Assyrian campaign (Isaiah 7), and, on another occasion, gave assurance to the Israelite king and his people that the Assyrians would surely be defeated by Yahweh (Isaiah 39). Jeremiah, during Nebuchadnezzar's attack on Jerusalem, was active in offering advice on how to prevent the impending doom. But his advice would fall on deaf ears, but at their peril (Jer. 42) (Rowley, 1976).
 5. ***The Prophet as Political Activists:*** An activist has been described as a person who in an event but also supports a policy with vigorous action. In light of this, the ancient Israelite prophets could be regarded as political activists. This is because they were actively involved in Israel's national political life. Their contribution to the shaping of the monarchy becomes obvious. They take active part in the appointment and deposition of kings. In Yahweh's name, they designate candidates for the throne and fight to keep them in place if necessary. Because of an infringement of the rituals of the holy war, the same Samuel who nominates the peasant farmer's son, Saul, to be king with the words, furthers also his rejection (I Samuel 10:1, 15:28) (Nissineh, 2002). Moreover, the end of Omri's dynasty was attributed to Prophet Elisha (Overholt, 1989). He was the one who cleansed the political terrain that had long been defiled by this dynasty (2 Kg 9:10).
 6. ***The Prophet and the Self:*** The prophet is equally human with some emotional and psychological challenges that can enhance and/or inhibit the prophetic ministry. For this reason, the prophet as a servant of YHWH is called to carry out YHWH's (not the prophet's) ministry through constant training and retraining, retreats and recollections. In this wise, some of the qualities that flows from such relationship will include humility, self-control, prudence, passion for inspirational creative abilities, sense of timing and rightness (Herbert, 1940). The

prophet is extremely prayerful (Is. 62:6), selfless (Dan. 5:13-17; 2 Kg 5:14-19; cf. 1Tim 3:3) and humble (Num. 12:3). The prophet trembles before the LORD, knowing full well that the secret of the LORD is with them that fear him; and he will reveal His covenant to them (Ps. 25:14). The fear of the LORD means to hate evil: pride and arrogance (Prov. 8:13).

The ancient prophets were not only messengers of God, but men committed to the one who sent them. Their ethical life and absolute obedience to God in face of hatred, opposition and persecution remain unquestionable. Yet they do not merely pass on the word which they have received from YHWH. They themselves were responsible for the message's correct delivery. The prophet's primary mission is to communicate the truth about YHWH, to warn and admonish in order that judgment may be averted and blessings incurred (Folarin, 2004). This mission is clearly demonstrated in their effort to call the Israelites back to the covenant, asking for change not only at the individual level but also at the social level. They act as the authentic custodian of the tradition of YHWH religion.

7. *Prophets Amos and Elijah are Tough and at Times Impatient with Sin:* they focus on their task as to execute it direct and raw without minding what happens thereafter. Their toughness and lack of pastoral patience may not be too comfortable for some congregations (Asha, 2012). They are also more concerned with social injustice and religious formalism. They considered each citizen responsible for dispensing justice (Mic. 6:8). Social and moral concern lay at the very heart of religion as far as the prophets are concerned. Hence, their repeated rebuke of idolatry and formalistic worship (Asha, 2010). Furthermore, the prophets Amos and Elijah are morally sound and are not susceptible or ensnared to outward sins such as adultery, stealing, cheating etc. they are strong in prayer; submissive and obedience to God's authority. The prophets are usually hated for their strong commitment to God's task and in most cases are target of Satan attack. Also, they often suffered isolation, opposition, betrayal, and attack as they prophesied to their people. They have no private life because they are Gods servant; have no feelings of their own or desires of their own apart from Gods desires for their lives. Their human rights lie with God (Jim and Murphy 1994).

Moral Decline of Pastoral Ministry in Nigeria

The proliferation of churches in the midst of crises of kidnapping, corruption, banditry, robbery, poverty and immorality in Nigeria is a contradiction. This section focuses on Nigerian society where profession of faith is not always translating to spirituality or does not correspond with morality. Nigerians are highly religious and viewed everything with religious sentiment. However, increase in pastors, religious activities and churches does not automatically lead to an improvement in moral behaviour. If true religious revival is a response to moral spiritual awakening, why is it that the moral life of many Nigerians is questionable both locally and internationally? If true religion is to justify the way of God to man and it has the function of assigning moral meaning to human experiences, why do many Christians not behave more morally? Adetunmibi inquired (2017). Thus, religiosity without morality is useless in the sight of God. The following are reasons for the moral shift of pastoral ministry in Nigeria:

Insufficient Biblical Knowledge: Many who are engaged in pastoral ministry in Nigeria are impoverished in their Biblical grounding (Biwul, 2018). They lack adequate biblical knowledge of the nature and function of the pastoral office. The Old Testament writings, the gospels, and the epistles are all expressed in clear pastoral tones because the scripture itself is an embodiment of God's love, and his purposeful agenda for humanity is good. Hence, the presence of misinformed and unguided people in the pastoral ministry distorts the biblical text and corrupts the ministry.

Self-centredness: Unfortunately, many pastors in pastoral ministry in Nigeria today are more self-centred than Christ-centred. Some pastors in Nigeria today publicly display and preach about their luxury cars, private jets, and cosy relationships with corrupt politicians, offering prophecies of election victories and protection for financial or political gain. However, prophets like Amos, Elijah and Jeremiah rebuffed every opportunity to live luxury life in order to be right with God. Some pastors in Nigeria today fail to pay careful attention to the functional descriptions of pastoral identity and the demands of the ministry (Biwui, 2018). they care more about their personal benefits than they do for the needs of church members. Therefore, when pastoral ministry is approached from a personal-benefit viewpoint rather than from a biblical perspective, a negative shift is unavoidable.

Love of Money: Another sorry state of many pastors in Nigeria is love of money. Love of money cuts across many things. Injustice, bribery, stealing by trick or force, fraud, money laundering, falsification of figures and results, impersonation, etc are all examples of corruption, and all aforementioned are obvious in all spheres of daily activities of Nigerians. Venality in society has also eaten deep among church leaders. As Fakeye observed that greed and immorality is not only among church people, but also among church leaders. He stresses that corruption are found even among the leaders of the Christian Association of Nigeria, the highest Christian body in Nigeria (2010).

Profit-Driven Preachers: Presently, Nigerian Churches are filled with various profit-driven preachers and strange doctrines. Preachers who preach false gospel and expectations to their members. They preach messages for financial gain and refuse to rebuke the nation. Ministerial respect is now based on the type of car the minister drives and the type of house he lives in (Adetunmibi, 2017). Consequently, as a result of this, many preachers cannot preach about character and holiness in their services and the few faithful preachers are unpopular in Nigeria (Oladimeji, 2007). David Enweremadu, a Nigerian economic strategist, maintains that despite all the efforts of the government to curb corruption, such as anti-corruption campaign policies and agencies, because the church is not involved, the government's anti-corruption efforts have not yielded much result (Enweremadu, 2012).

Neglect of Integrity and Character: Moreover, moral character and integrity are essential virtues for the pastorate according to Onwuka (2011). People in pastoral ministry neglect this to their peril and to the detriment of the ministry. As a result, their focus has shifted from the basics of winning souls and working hard to build up church members' faith to a desire to derive material benefits from the ministry.

Materialism: The rise of materialism among some pastors has led to their being described as "Men of Gold" rather than Men of God. They are the Gehazis of today, who are not concerned with spiritual matters but with material ones (Zachariah, 2013). Materialistic ministers resort to coercion, manipulation, threats and dictatorial behaviour to squeeze more financial and material gain from their congregation.

Satan-Focused Preaching: This is a kind of preaching that solely focuses on evil spirits rather than God in order to terrify congregants into giving or

obedience, which many pastors in “White Garment” churches, some Pentecostal and African Indigenous Churches, have leveraged upon to exploit their members and make them perpetually subservient. Furthermore, blaming spiritual powers for one’s crimes or misbehaviour is another poor state of the Nigerian society. Africans generally believe that spiritual powers can influence people’s actions positively or negatively. Meyer argues that social and immoral behaviours are explained by reference to Satan or the Devil. For people to be culpable for their actions, the gospel message should go beyond this dualistic teaching of God and Satan and bear less emphasis on Satan (1999). For this reason, every person should be ready to take responsibility for their actions. When people think about the consequences of their actions, they will be careful in their doing.

Ethical Example of Prophets Elijah, Amos and Jeremiah as Framework to Pastoral Moral Decline in Nigeria

The credibility of Christian leadership is hinged on their ability to regulate personal ethical behaviour. This directly points to an ethical lifestyle of integrity. The Old Testament provides sufficient ethical resources for social justice and care for the poor, the widow, the orphan, the oppressed and the marginalised. Also, the prophets condemned several practices, such as bribery, fraud, extortion, greed, and dishonesty, which result in a violation of the covenant relationship between God and His people. God repeatedly redirected His people to ethical behaviours that exemplify justice, equity and fairness (Jacob & Simon, 2021).

Therefore, Nigerian pastors, like the Old Testament prophets, should set an example through their conduct and activities, ensuring that all they do aligns with biblical norms and principles. They should put structures in place that ensure transparency and accountability in the management of the church’s financial resources; deepen their spirituality and that of the church members by teaching, preaching, and running programmes that focus more on developing Christian and godly character rather than materialism. In addition, like the O.T prophets, pastors in Nigeria need to imbibe and exhibit the following traits and qualities: love (1 Pet. 1:22); teachability (Col. 3:16); servant-leadership (Mark 10:35-37); accountability (Heb. 3:13); mercy (Luke 6:35); submission (1 Thess. 5:12-13); grace (2 Cor. 8:7-9). And pastoral ministry needs to be sanitised by sound theological training, anchoring ministries in the scriptures rather than in human

charisma or cultural superstition. The success of pastoral ministry in Nigeria should be evaluated by the integrity and fruit of the pastoral, not just by miracles or wealth, as Apostle Paul advocated in his pastoral ethics. Some of the ethical lifestyle of O.T. prophets aforementioned earlier in this paper are religious guardian, toughness against sin, social reformer, political activist, boundary figure and mediator and many more, hence, the implications of these virtues to pastoral ministry in Nigeria are that pastors should stand between God and people with courage, not compromise; they must reject idolatry, materialism and syncretism to uphold true worship; more so, pastors must speak against injustice, corruption, exploitation of the poor and oppressive leadership most especially in Nigeria of today where governments and politicians are callous, oppressive, blood thirsty; further, contemporary pastors like the Old Testament prophets must offer godly counsel on national and moral issues, not just personal gain, and confront evil directly even at personal cost without fear of persecution; and live in absolute obedience, prayerfulness and submission to God's authority, engage in national transformation, hold leaders accountable and advocate for justice.

Conclusion

The ethical example of Old Testament prophets marked by integrity, advocacy for justice, and absolute obedience to God, offers a powerful corrective to moral decline in Nigerian pastoral ministry. Many Nigerian pastors have drifted toward materialism, love of money and self-centeredness, abandoning the prophetic call to social justice and spiritual leadership. By returning to the biblical model of prophets like Elijah, Isaiah, Jeremiah and Amos, pastors can restore their credibility, transform society and fulfil their God-given role as moral guides and nation-builders.

Recommendations

The paper strongly recommends the following practical steps toward prophetic reformation:

- i. Seminaries must mandate courses on prophetic ethics, using Elijah, Amos and Jeremiah as case studies, and institutionalised financial integrity paired with mentoring groups for pastoral accountability.
- ii. Following Elijah and Amos, who defended the poor against royal abuse, Nigerian pastors should also lead a campaign against the exploitation

- of the poor, police brutality and oppressive leadership in Nigerian governments and agencies.
- iii. More so, pastors must eschew materialism, greed, and love of money, and embrace servant-leadership, and uphold integrity in order to be respected and for national transformation.
 - iv. Contemporary Nigerian pastors must confront evil directly without fear of persecution, denouncing injustice, bribery, embezzlement and favoritism.

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